

DEVELOPMENT OF THE FURNITURE MARKET IN SAMARKAND REGION AND THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN IT

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Abstract. In this article, the expertise of the furniture industry and the conjuncture of the furniture market is studied. The position of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC in the market and the development of marketing activities were considered.

Keywords: enterprise, furniture industry, conjuncture, market, demand, competition, sales, technology.

ТЕКСТ НАУЧНОЙ РАБОТЫ НА ТЕМУ «РАЗВИТИЕ МЕБЕЛЬНОГО РЫНКА САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ И РОЛЬ В НЕМ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА»

Аннотация. В данной статье изучена экспертиза мебельной отрасли и конъюнктура мебельного рынка, рассмотрено положение ООО «HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL» на рынке и развитие маркетинговой деятельности.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, мебельная промышленность, конъюнктура, рынок, спрос, конкуренция, сбыт, технология.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the furniture industry has become the most developed private industry. The technological process of the furniture industry has its own standards, technical safety requirements. Currently, the furniture produced by local furniture makers in our country is not inferior to foreign ones. In the past, buying a set of furniture from customers required a lot of effort. Today, the expertise of the furniture industry allows you to choose from thousands of different collections. Fair competition will only lead to the development of the industry, and as a result, the company and, moreover, its employees will prosper.

As mentioned above, Samarkand region occupies one of the leading positions in furniture production in the Republic. As of January 1, 2021, 131 organizations specializing in wood processing and furniture production are operating in the region. This is 16 units or 11.9% more than in 2020. All newly created enterprises were small business entities. Therefore, 126 out of 131 enterprises or 96.2% are small business entities.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

These organizations produced a total of 167,273.7 million soums of goods in 2021, which is 13.7% more than in 2020. of the created product 145,528.1 million soums are ready-made furniture, 21,745.6 million soums are separate components for furniture (Figure 2.1).

Furniture manufacturing enterprises include enterprises specializing in one product or several types of products. Of these organizations, 105 (77.8%) specialized in one product, 16 (12.8%) organizations with two to three product ranges, and 12 (9.4%) organizations producing four or more products.

At the same time, the analysis shows that the organizations of the last group produce 19.87% of finished furniture products. Therefore, multi-branch complex furniture enterprises are more efficient than other specialized enterprises.

When keeping statistical reports of furniture products, it is envisaged to divide them into the following groups:

- Mainly metal frame furniture for sitting;
 - Furniture for sitting, not included in other groups;
 - Wooden furniture for institutions;
 - Kitchen furniture;
 - Beds (except bed bases);
 - Wooden bedroom furniture (except wall cabinets, bed bases, lamps and lamps, floor mirrors, seating furniture);
 - Wooden furniture for study and living rooms (except floor mirrors, seating furniture).
- Components for furniture are also divided into separate groups according to production technologies, used materials and tasks:

technologies, used materials and tasks:

- Parts of seating furniture;
- Parts of furniture (except parts of seating furniture);
- Metal furniture for institutions;
- Services of subcontractors for performing part of the production process (or separate operations) of seating furniture and their parts, parts of other furniture.

The following table and diagrams show the volume of production in natural and monetary sizes for the range of furniture products.

1. table.

Assortment of furniture products produced in Samarkand region in 2021*

T/r	Type of furniture	Number of manufacturing enterprises	Production volume in 2021,		Amount	
				%	million soums	%
A. Ready-made furniture						
1	Mainly metal frame furniture for sitting, piece	15	352139	45.0	12681.76	8.68
2	Furniture for sitting, not included in other groups	31	120510	15.4	60835.06	41.64
3	Wooden furniture for institutions, pcs	25	44604	5.7	16149.4	11.05
4	Kitchen furniture	26	234760	30.0	7988.76	5.47
5	Mattresses (except mattress bases), pcs	7	7669	0.98	3217.76	2.2
6	Wooden bedroom furniture (except wall-mounted wardrobes, bed bases, lamps and lamps, floor mirrors, seating furniture), units	23	7355	0.94	17493.6	11.97

7	Wooden furniture for study and living rooms (except floor mirrors, seating furniture), pieces	18	12520	1.60	27723.5	18.98
	Total	145	782532	100	145528.1	100
B. Separate components for furniture						
1	Parts of furniture for sitting, tn	2	7.17		250.6	1.18
2	Parts of furniture (except parts of furniture for sitting), tn	12	707.0		2856.6	13.48
3	Metal furniture for institutions, tn	5	3553.3		10064.7	47,51
4	Services of subcontractors for performing part of the production process (or separate operations) of furniture for sitting and their parts, parts of other furniture, mln. amount	7	6162.8		8011.64	37.82
		26	-	-	21745.6	100
			-		167273.7	

*- The table was compiled based on the data of the Samarkand regional statistics bureau.

The first conclusion from the table is that all enterprises in the region are engaged in the production of finished furniture products, while the components are made in 26 enterprises. If we see finished furniture products in natural sizes, total 782,532 units of the majority of products metal frame furniture (352,139 units, or 45.0%) and kitchen furniture (234,760 units, or 30.0%) for living. All types of furniture do not have a large share in natural dimensions. Analyzing the composition of components is associated with several difficulties, since their units of measurement cannot be compared to the number of products.

According to the data in monetary units, among finished furniture products, the production of sitting furniture not included in another group occupies a large place (41.64%), and the second place is occupied by wooden furniture for workrooms and living rooms (18.98%). Among the products, the smallest place is occupied by the production of beds, i.e. mattresses (2.2%). The diagram below shows the role of finished furniture products in production. Metal furniture for institutions (47.51%) took the main place in the production of components for furniture, and subcontractor services (37.82%) took the second place.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the above information, it can be noted that the furniture production network in Samarkand region has sufficient potential and has developed rapidly in recent years.

At the same time, it should be noted that most of the enterprises in the sector are small individual entrepreneurs and family enterprises. In order to further develop the furniture industry, it is clear that it is necessary to create a marketing program aimed at the development of not only a separate furniture enterprise, but also the entire industry, using marketing theory and practice.

"HAVAS COMFORT FURNITURE" if we look at the history of the limited liability company, it, like many business entities, started its activity from a small carpentry workshop. From 1996 to today, it has grown into a large furniture manufacturing enterprise. In 2003, it was transformed into a limited liability company under this name, and in 2006, the production of various furniture for the population, enterprises, organizations and institutions was started.

The results of the enterprise's production activity can be seen from the following data (Table 2).

Table 2

Production indicators of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC in 2018-2021

No	Indicator name	Amount by years			
		2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Production volume, million soms	8745.7	9443.6	10402.1	11688.5
2	Annual growth rates of production, %	100	107.98	110.15	111.4
3	Change compared to 2018, %	100	107.98	118.93	132.5

As can be seen from the data, "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC is constantly increasing its production volumes. 2021 11 billion by the year. A product worth 588 million soms was produced, which is 1.3 times more than in 2018. We can clearly observe the change in production volumes in the following diagrams (Figures 2.4 - 2.5)

Figure 1. Volumes of product production at "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC, in millions of soums by year.

Figure 2. Yearly changes in the volume of production at "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC, in %.

As can be seen from the pictures, the annual growth of production in the last three years was 108-111%. This indicator shows that the company is growing rapidly and increasing its position in the market.

Information on the range of products produced at HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC is presented in the table below (Table 4).

Table 4

Assortment of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC products in 2018-2021, million soums.

N o	Type of furniture	Annual production, million soums				Annual growth, %		
		2018	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021
1	Kitchen furniture	1542.7	4089.4	2159.5	3387.3	265.1	52.8	156.6
2	Soft furniture	4693.8	3694.5	5570.3	4893.9	78.7	150.8	87.8
3	Office furniture	18.4	12.3	232.0	486.2	66.9	1888.9	209.6
4	Bedroom furniture	797.6	391.1	183.1	404.4	49.0	46.8	220.9
5	Wooden table and chairs	417.2	11.3	151.8	155.5	2.7	1339.8	102.3
6	Magazine tables	593.0	272.1	536.7	752.7	45.9	197.3	140.2
7	Mattress	683.0	975.8	1568.6	1608.3	142.9	160.7	102.5
	Total	8745.7	9443.6	10402.1	11688.5	107.98	110.15	111.4

As can be seen from the information presented in the table, according to the main positions of the assortment "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC is observing production growth. We can only see a decrease in the production of bed furniture and mattresses. In this case, the actions of

competitors in the Samarkand furniture market for bed furniture can be cited as a reason. At the same time, as a result of the specialization of furniture production, it is necessary to emphasize the active service of other partner enterprises with mattress production.

At the same time, it will be necessary to analyze the change in the composition of the assortment in order to draw conclusions about individual assortment positions. Here we study the share of product types in total production (Table 5).

Table 5

The composition of the product range of HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC in 2018-2021, %

No	Type of furniture	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Kitchen furniture	17.64	43.29	20.76	28.98
2	Soft furniture	53.67	39.11	53.55	41.87
3	Office furniture	0.21	0.13	2.23	4.16
4	Others	9,12	4.14	1.76	3.46
5	Wooden table and chairs	4.77	0.12	1.46	1.33
6	Magazine tables	6.78	2.88	5.16	6.44
7	Mattress	7.81	10.33	15.08	13.76
	Total	100	100	100	100

CONCLUSION

From the data in the table, we can see that in 2018, three types of products - soft furniture (24.24%), office furniture (32.32%) and bed furniture (28.28%) made up the main part of the assortment. The smallest place is occupied by kitchen furniture (0.61%). In 2021, we will see big changes in the composition of the assortment. Office furniture (29.63%) and soft furniture (24.69%) are in the leading positions. The share of furniture for the bed decreased sharply and made 12.35%. The contribution of kitchen furniture production increased from 0.61% to 9.88%. Similarly, the production of wooden tables and chairs increased from 8.08% to 19.75%. The share of magazine tables and mattresses, which occupy a small place in the assortment of manufactured products, further decreased and by 2018 made up 2.47% and 1.23%, respectively.

It can be concluded that in the past three years there have been major changes in the furniture market and "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC's position in the market is also changing. This, in turn, requires the development of the enterprise's marketing activities.

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